

Net Zero DRI Case Studies Report

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Executive summary

As part of the Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project, a case study was undertaken on the STFC-operated facilities JASMIN and Scafell Pike/JADE 2 (these latter being part of the Hartree Centre). Interviews were held with managers of these facilities, based on a structured script, to explore their current concerns and future expectations with respect to Net Zero. A systematic SWOT analysis was performed on the results of the interviews, leading to a number of findings and recommendations that appear to be of general relevance and validity to Net Zero and DRI, in the following areas:

- power monitoring
- management of energy contracts
- user practices and behaviours
- local sources of energy and use of heat
- opportunities in technological developments
- principles of procurement
- knowledge base on data centre design

1. Introduction

According to the proposal for the Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Scoping Project, the case studies of exemplar national and international infrastructures were intended to inform the design of the database of UKRI DRI as well as to consider the implications of the broad scope of these centralised resources. Work began in earnest in May 2022 and continued to the end of the project in March 2023.

The present report describes one side of the case studies, based on interviews with DRI managers of selected infrastructures, and presents the findings and recommendations. A second strand of work, undertaken by the Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre (EPCC), took a different approach, investigating the carbon emissions and efficiency of the ARCHER2 high-performance service, and this is described in a separate report.

Work on these interview-based case studies has, as envisaged, proceeded together with the design of the questionnaire for gathering information by survey on the UKRI DRI landscape. Cross-checking was done between the two to ensure completeness and appropriateness of coverage. The results of the case studies do indeed shed light on the priorities, constraints and issues faced by managers of these centralised resources, which might not be the same as those faced by for example university or department-level service managers. The hope is that the findings and recommendations may be used in conjunction with outcomes of other parts of the project to present a coherent way forward on the path to Net Zero.

2. The approach to the case studies

The method adopted for the case studies is illustrated in the following figure.

Step 1. Selection of DRIs

Three DRIS (two of them within the same centre and so treated together) were chosen for the interview-based case studies on the grounds of their close connections with the Net Zero project team and their representation of different types of national-level infrastructures. The selected DRIs were:

- JASMIN, the UK's data analysis facility for environmental science;
- Scafell Pike and JADE 2, part of the service offered by the Hartree Centre.

Step 2. Preparation of interview scripts

It was important to adopt a uniform and clearly motivated basis for the interviews, covering the current concerns and future expectations of DRI managers with respect to Net Zero in a way that was both general and allowed for exploring detail where appropriate. The structure shown in the figures below was developed: four groups of questions, each (apart from the last, about user communities) with different temporal perspectives ("now" and "possible future"), leading to a set of questions directly usable with the interviewees. The questions about the future were divided into short-term (the next few years) and long-term (up to 20 years).

The intent of this structure was to understand the information that DRI managers have available, their actual practices in running the DRI, the external factors that constrain or influence them, and the nature of their user communities. The specific questions served as an entry point to gain information and explore the issues in as much depth as was appropriate.

The full interview script is reproduced in Annex A.

	Now	Possible future
What is known?	<i>What is measured/ monitored Data available</i>	<i>What could/should be measured</i>
What is done?	<i>Current operations</i>	<i>Scope for action</i>
What is the external environment? (technological change, user behaviour, policy trends, ...)	<i>Current constraints and drivers</i>	<i>Future opportunities and threats</i>
User communities	<i>Characteristics of users, problems they try to solve, techniques used, etc.</i>	

Similarities and differences

Some additional questions were also asked as follow-up in some cases. These concerned machine room design and its impact on energy usage and efficiency, and whether DRI is more efficient if it is consolidated and centralised. These questions are also presented in Annex A.

Step 3. Conduct of interviews

Interviews were arranged with managers of the respective DRIs, either just one or two together. Generally one member of the Net Zero project team would lead the interviewing, following the script and exploring the issues, with a second team member taking notes. These notes provided the raw material for the next step of the process. The interviews were typically around an hour in duration.

Step 4. Reports on interviews

The raw notes on each interview were expanded into more coherent text and placed into the template of the questionnaire, giving a set of Word files with a uniform structure.

Step 5. Analysis of interviews

The analysis step is key to the value of the case studies. A number of principles underpinned the analysis:

- Systematic approach—not just plucking out points arbitrarily
- Generalisation—understanding what can be concluded more widely from the interviews about particular DRIs
- Validation—some confidence in the correctness of the analysis

It was decided to apply SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)—that is, to identify and highlight SWOTs (always in the context of Net Zero and environmental concerns more generally) within the interview reports. This approach fits well with the structure of the interview script, and with the need for evidence and recommendations. Strengths represent positive features of the current state of affairs (for example high-quality reliable information available), while weaknesses capture known deficiencies (for example, missing or unreliable information). Opportunities and threats relate to possible futures: opportunities as positive developments that could be brought about if suitable actions were taken; threats as possible undesirable situations that might arise.

Each case study report was therefore reviewed and annotated with SWOTs. This was not simply a mechanical exercise, but required interpretation and knowledge of the context, but it seemed to work well

and the SWOTs emerged naturally. Finally, a master table was produced, bringing together the identified SWOTs grouped in themes and where possible aligned across the case studies (so helping with the generalisation and validation principles). This table is reproduced in section 5 below. The chosen themes were:

- energy supply;
- energy consumption;
- equipment procurement and lifecycle;
- technological developments;
- user behaviour and expectations;
- higher level policies and guidance.

Step 6. Conclusions and recommendations

From the grouped and aligned SWOTs emerge a number of findings that appear to be of general relevance and validity to Net Zero and DRI. As for the extraction of SWOTs themselves, the identification of these findings is not an exact science, and other interpretations may be possible. However, an important consequence is that each finding should imply a recommendation—and the production of recommendations was one of the success criteria for the whole Net Zero DRI Scoping Project. The SWOT method lends itself well to identifying recommendations: Strengths should be sustained and built on, Weaknesses countered, Opportunities capitalised on, and Threats avoided.

3. Overview of the case study DRIs

JASMIN (<https://jasmin.ac.uk/>) is the UK's data analysis facility for environmental science, providing both compute and storage facilities for data-intensive research. It is a highly versatile infrastructure supporting over 1500 users exploring a wide range of topics in environmental science and engaged in a variety of workflows. Offerings include development and running of analysis codes, long-term data curation services, high-throughput data transfers, hosting services for environmental science, and delivering training. JASMIN is operated by STFC on behalf of NERC.

Some key facts about JASMIN (these were obtained from the survey questionnaire of DRIs, which was also completed for the case study DRIs):

- 14000 processing cores, 800 physical servers, total storage 153 Pb
- Annual energy consumption 2500 MWh
- Air cooled
- Average PUE 1.31 but varies over year from 1.15 on coldest days to nearly 1.5 on hottest

The two DRIs known as Scafell Pike and JADE 2 are both part of the service offered by the Hartree Centre (<https://www.hartree.stfc.ac.uk/>), which is devoted to the exploitation of supercomputing, data science and artificial intelligence technologies for the benefit of UK business and industry, and is part of STFC. Scafell Pike is a HPC facility that supports modelling and simulation for engineering, computational chemistry, physics and some life sciences work, while JADE 2 is a GPU cluster with heavy AI application usage. Both are managed by STFC's Digital Infrastructure department.

Some key facts about Scafell Pike/JADE 2:

- 25728 Intel SkyLake cores in Scafell Pike, around 500 physical servers in total, 21 Pb storage
- Annual energy consumption estimated 6 MWh
- Scafell Pike uses direct liquid cooling; JADE has liquid-cooled rear-door heat exchangers.
- PUE ranges between 1.2 and 1.4

The following table lists the interviews that took place.

Date	Case study DRI	Interviewee(s)
1 Aug 2022	JASMIN	Interviewees 1 and 2
21 Sep 2022	Scafell Pike/JADE 2	Interviewee 3
3 Oct 2022	Scafell Pike/JADE 2	Interviewee 4
7 Dec 2022	Scafell Pike/JADE 2	Interviewee 4 (follow-up)

4. SWOT analysis

The table below is the result of Step 5 of the procedure, bringing together the SWOTs in themes, with a view to identifying commonalities and differences to assist with validation, further analysis and reporting. In a handful of cases an important point was made but it was not clear whether it represented a Strength, Weakness, Opportunity or Threat; these cases are identified with an initial question mark. A few SWOTs have been duplicated across themes when this seemed appropriate, and an attempt has been made to match recurring points across the case studies in the same or neighbouring rows.

JASMIN (Interviewees 1 and 2)	Scafell Pike/JADE 2 (Interviewee 3)	Scafell Pike/JADE 2 (Interviewee 4)
Theme: Energy supply		
		?: Carbon offsetting <i>[price paid for energy includes carbon offset]</i>
?: Buffered from electricity suppliers <i>[supply managed by UKRI Energy Manager]</i>	W: Disconnect of management of DRI from sources of energy <i>[no say in where energy sourced]</i>	?: Buffered from electricity suppliers. <i>[only told unit cost; prices set 12-18 months in advance]</i>
		?: Level of decision making <i>[on sourcing power, currently STFC level]</i>
		O: Flexibility of different tariffs for different times of day
		O: Possibility of on-site renewables
		O: Possibility of battery use
?: Significance of UPS (now and in future) <i>[criticality of systems; relation of UPS to e.g. back-up generators]</i>	O: Direct connection to grid to avoid energy loss <i>[i.e. not through UPS?]</i>	S: Efficiency of UPS increases with use
	O: Local sources of energy/cooling <i>[ground water, solar cell]</i>	O: Excess heat available for other purposes
Theme: Energy consumption		
S: Informative power usage monitoring (also following paragraphs) <i>[monitoring at quite fine granularity, with dashboard]</i>	S: Good variety of power measurements available	O: Different levels/granularity of monitoring

O: Power usage of software <i>[it is possible, though not standardised]</i>	W: ... but not all power meters provide useful/valid data <i>[not all readings collected, some meters fail, other not customised]</i>	
O: Splitting power usage in different ways (but note difficulties) <i>[interesting to divide by type of storage, but would need more kit]</i>	W: Monitoring may be for other purposes than just recording power consumption <i>[e.g. diagnosis]</i>	
W: Unavailability or unreliability of some levels of power monitoring - also following paragraphs <i>[measure at PDU level because component level not available]</i>		
W: Cooling somewhat separated from actual IT infrastructure <i>[cooling not covered in dashboard]</i>	O: Different/newer types of cooling	W/O: Impact of cooling / Potential to reduce cooling
?: Trend to liquid cooling only	O: Local sources of energy/cooling <i>[ground water, solar cell]</i>	O: Location of DRI in cold environments for cheap cooling
		O: Design of buildings for reuse of heat
		W/O: Thermal properties of building materials <i>[implications for cooling and heat reuse]</i>
	O: Energy-aware job scheduling	O: Intelligent scheduling taking account of power draw/cost.
?: Storage vs compute <i>[temporary vs. Persistent storage, read/write, networking]</i>		
Theme: Equipment procurement and lifecycle		
W: Financial constraints lead to short-term decisions <i>[e.g. spend needed by end of financial year]</i>	?: Balancing priorities <i>[including maintenance]</i>	?: Comparison of maintenance costs with cost of replacement <i>[what is trade-off as kit gets older?]</i>
	T: Existing DRIs constrained n what new solutions can be implemented	
	?: DRIs can change over time, for better or worse <i>[converging on or diverging from Net Zero]</i>	W: Decreasing use causes PUE to increase.
		T: Lower usage of older technology.
W: Design decisions relating to old data centres are lost over time		W/O: Lack of specific body of knowledge on data centre design—maybe could be codified

		<i>[best practice from other institutions]</i>
Theme: Technological developments		
O: Workflow related to carbon cost <i>[workflow design tools to model this?]</i>		
O: Possible application/adaptation of "Green Algorithms" (EMBL-EBI)	O: Energy-aware job scheduling	O: Intelligent scheduling taking account of power draw/cost
O: Shift in hardware to more energy efficient types <i>[e.g. ARM]</i>	O: Possibly running at higher temperatures	
	O: New processors [?]	
	O: Other emerging options <i>[commercial solutions, batteries]</i>	
Theme: Use behaviour and expectations		
		W: Lack of connection with users and their behaviour <i>[monitor system consumption, not user usage]</i>
	T: Potential impact on service levels to users <i>[of actions taken by infrastructure management]</i>	W: Limited flexibility in downtime <i>[needs careful planning and advance notice]</i>
S: Workshops for users on efficient resource use		
S: Workshops to encourage best practice among users		
O: Case studies to help communicate with users		
S/O: Sharing of models with communities <i>[i.e. reuse]</i>		
S/W: Some optimisation of algorithms by users, but limited		
W: Little information about efficiency/optimisation of what users do <i>[whether running efficient code, or using platform in an optimised way]</i>		
O: Informing users of energy they consumed (not currently possible)		
Theme: Higher level policies and guidance		
O/T: Changing basis of procurement to give weight to environmental factors		

O: Idea of "pool" for infrastructure [<i>provisioning from UKRI pool</i>]		
		?: Level of decision making [<i>on sourcing power, currently STFC level</i>]
		S: Better resilience of centralised systems

5. Conclusions

The following table brings together the concluding findings from the SWOT analysis, selected to conform to the principles of generalisation and validation that underpinned the analysis. Each finding has an associated recommendation, responding to the positive or negative features expressed in the finding and expressed in actionable form. It can be seen that many of the recommendations correspond to those found in the DRI mapping survey, which is reassuring.

Finding	Consequent recommendations
There is generally comprehensive power monitoring of the case study DRIs, though not necessarily at a level that would give the most useful and actionable information to enable environmentally aware management of the DRI.	Best practice should be shared among DRI managers, and those responsible for design and procurement, on suitable levels of monitoring power usage and how this may be effectively deployed in practice. Cf. REC 11 from report on mapping survey: "Provide guidance and support for facility managers to enable them to develop and deploy systems for monitoring and reporting energy usage."
There is a disconnect of management of the DRIs from the sources of energy: contracts with suppliers are negotiated at higher levels of the organisation, prices are set in advance, the price is a simple unit price regardless of time of day.	A recommendation to devolve management of energy contracts to individual DRI managers would be impractical and undesirable. However the negotiation of contracts, at whatever level it takes place, should take account of the patterns of usage at DRI level with a view to opportunities for optimisation. Cf. REC 6 from report on mapping survey: "Some parts of the community have demonstrated that purchasing renewable energy can be combined with financial and scientific success. UKRI should consider a policy of purchasing electricity from renewable sources across the entire DRI. Experience and knowledge should be shared in relation to on-site renewable energy generation."
There is a lack of direct connection with users and their behaviour: users' practices and energy consumption are not known.	It is not necessarily the job of DRI managers to interact with users or to have in-depth awareness of user practices. However, monitoring of energy use related in some way to user activity would complement the general usage monitoring. The possible scope and implementation of such monitoring should be examined and disseminated. Cf. REC 12 from report on mapping survey:

	<p>“Develop a fair approach for recording, monitoring and reporting energy usage information at appropriate levels (e.g. per job, per user, per group, per research theme). NOTE: It was pointed out that there may be unforeseen negative consequences of making energy usage information public (or within institution) – it could be used to shame a high-energy user. A solution must be carefully managed to avoid such outcomes.”</p>
<p>There is a strong awareness of opportunities such as local sources of energy or use of heat, but limited ability to implement them.</p>	<p>Any practice and experience should be shared on local sources of energy and heat reuse, leading to a knowledge base on costs and opportunities. Cf. REC 7 from report on mapping survey: “Engage with respondents that have heat re-use systems in place. Look for opportunities for knowledge exchange to make heat re-use into standard practice for UKRI.”</p>
<p>Many opportunities are seen in technological developments (energy-efficient hardware, higher operating temperatures, energy-aware job scheduling ...), but DRI managers’ focus means that without direct mandate then ambitions will not translate to action.</p>	<p>DRI managers should be encouraged to identify technological opportunities with implications for Net Zero attainment; job roles should include this explicitly. Cf. REC 14 from report on mapping survey: “Net Zero needs to become an explicit and significant part of everyone's job. Staff need to know that taking action on sustainability is expected, recognised, respected and rewarded by their institutions and teams.”</p>
<p>Regarding procurement and upgrades, flexibility and potential for innovation is restricted by financial constraints, the need to balance priorities, and the established principles of the procurement process.</p>	<p>Principles and priorities of procurement should be re-examined to assess their alignment with Net Zero goals, within the necessary constraints. No corresponding REC in report on mapping survey.</p>
<p>There is a lack of a visible knowledge base and knowledge sharing on data centre design that could help with disseminating best practice and awareness of opportunities.</p>	<p>A central shared knowledge base on data centre design and best practice should be developed, with input from DRI managers, and sustained into the future with mechanisms to influence actual practice. No corresponding REC in report on mapping survey.</p>

Annex A: The interview script for use with the case studies

Group A: "What is known?"

Note: Much of the information about the first question might have been gathered separately for the purpose of building the database of infrastructures.

What do you currently measure or monitor?

- (a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?
- (b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

In the short term (the next few years), what do you think could or should be measured or monitored?

- (a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?
- (b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

Why?

It might not be necessary or useful to ask about the long-term view of this aspect.

In the long term (up to 20 years) ...

Group B: "What is done?"

To what extent do you currently take environmental considerations (energy efficiency, carbon footprint) into account in daily operations?

- (a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?
- (b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

In the short term (the next few years), do you think there is scope for changing the way you operate to respond more to environmental considerations?

- (a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?
- (b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

What would need to change to enable this to happen?

In the long term (up to 20 years) what new opportunities do you see for a thorough adaptation or redesign of operations giving priority to environmental considerations?

- (a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?
- (b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

What would need to change to enable this to happen?

Group C: “What is the external environment?”

What are the major current constraints and drivers (outside your direct control) that influence the environmental impact of your operations? For example: government or funder policies, user behaviour, technology constraints.

(a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?

(b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

In the short term (the next few years), do you see any changes coming in the external environment that could influence (positively or negatively) the environmental impact?

(a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?

(b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

In the long term (up to 20 years), can you envisage any more sweeping changes that could have an influence?

(a) relating to sources of the energy you consume?

(b) relating to usage of the energy (i.e. how it is consumed)?

Group D: “User communities”

We are interested in the user communities that access each of the facilities/services. Here are a set of questions related to the users:

- How would you describe your user communities?
 - Are they single-discipline or multi-discipline?
- What are the broad categories of problems that they trying to solve?
- What kinds of algorithms/technologies/software do they require?
 - Do you provide these as common resources?
 - Does that improve efficiency?
- Do the users employ a small number of optimised and established codes, or a large range of heterogeneous codes?
- Do you know if your users are running efficient code and using your services efficiently?
- (How) do you engage with your users to reduce their environmental impact?
 - Do you have the expertise/resource/time to advise your users on how to reduce their impact?
- Do you have a mechanism for telling your users how much energy they have consumed per unit of work?
- What would your users like to do that they can't do now?

Additional follow-up questions

As well as the main script reproduced above, some additional follow-up questions were asked in some cases.

Machine Room Design and its impact on energy usage and efficiency:

- Explore whether there are tangible impacts in choices made about how a machine room is designed/located/laid out/built etc.
- What is known/done etc.? E.g. best practice.
- What could/should be done?
- What evidence do they have to support statements?

Is DRI more efficient if it is consolidated and centralised? It is believed that centralising DRI will improve the energy efficiency of scientific work, but we do not necessarily have any hard evidence.

- Can the Case Study responders give us some insight and evidence on this topic?
- Can they point us to citable sources to back up this point, or their own experience or monitoring outputs?